

Comparison of speech-test configurations in unaided and aided conditions

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Abstract

Objective:

Analysis of the effect of different speech-test configurations on hearing-aid benefit.

Design:

Unaided and aided speech recognition of the Freiburg monosyllabic speech test (FMST) and speech-recognition thresholds (SRT) for the Oldenburg sentence test (OLSA) and Oldenburg Phrases (OLPHRA) taking German guidelines for hearing-aid validation into account in Experiment 1. Variations of the noise type, speakers' gender, speech synthesis, and presentation level for OLSA and OLPHRA in Experiment 2.

Study sample:

Experiment 1: 23 hearing-impaired participants (aged 61 - 79 years) with an average threshold at 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz (PTA-4) between 45.6 and 64.4 dB HL.

Experiment 2: 23 hearing-impaired participants (aged 60 - 78 years) with a PTA-4 between 44.4 and 67.5 dB HL.

Results:

In Experiment 1, OLPHRA measured the largest hearing-aid benefit, resulting from higher unaided SRTs than OLSA. In comparison to OLSA and OLPHRA, FMST showed limitations in measuring a hearing-aid benefit. Experiment 2 revealed that speech material, speakers' gender, and noise level, but not noise type and speech synthesis, significantly affected speech recognition and the measurable hearing-aid benefit.

Conclusion:

Using a female speaker and a low noise level maximised the hearing-aid effect. The greatest hearing-aid benefit was measured using OLPHRA.

Keywords: hearing-aid validation, hearing-aid benefit, speech recognition, phrase test, synthetic speech

Introduction

Hearing aids aim to improve speech-recognition abilities and, in general, the auditory function in everyday-life listening environments. Often, the hearing-aid fitting process involves standardised speech-recognition tests such as word or sentence tests, with an interfering noise and conducted at specific signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) and sound levels. Typically, three types of speech-recognition tests are used to validate hearing aids: word tests, matrix sentences tests, and everyday sentences tests. A common speech-recognition test using monosyllabic words is the Northwestern University Auditory Test No. 6 (NU6; Tillman & Carhart, 1966). The words have a consonant-vowel-consonant structure and are spoken by a male speaker. For presentation level, Stoppenbach et al. (1999) used, for example, a constant level of 40 dB HL to establish a reference curve for competing speech. The matrix sentence test was developed by Hagerman (1982) for the Swedish language using a female speaker. The sentences are constructed by randomly selecting words from a matrix consisting of 50 words in total and with ten alternatives for each position of the fixed structure: name-verb-number-adjective-object. The SNR for a speech-recognition score of 50% (Speech-Recognition Threshold, SRT) is measured in an adaptive procedure with a fixed speech level of 65 dB SPL. The importance of the matrix sentence test is demonstrated by its availability in many different languages (Kollmeier et al., 2015). A widely used everyday sentence test is the Hearing in Noise Test (HINT; Nilsson et al., 1994). The sentences are spoken by a male speaker. As in the Hagerman speech test, the SRT is measured in an adaptive procedure, but with a fixed noise level of 72 dB (A). This test is also available in many other languages, e.g. in German (Joiko et al., 2021; Mönnich et al., 2023). These three general types of speech-recognition tests show fundamental differences in their configuration with respect to the structure, speaker, and presentation level. This work aims to investigate the effect of differences in speech-test configurations on the measured hearing-aid benefit.

In Germany, the hearing-aid guidelines (G-BA, 2025) specify which speech-recognition tests and settings have to be used in the context of hearing-aid validation. Thus, one of the following speech-recognition tests must be considered: the Freiburg monosyllabic speech test (FMST; Hahlbrock, 1953), the Oldenburg sentence test (OLSA; Wagener et al., 1999), or the Göttingen sentence test (GÖSA; Kollmeier & Wesselkamp, 1997). The FMST consists of monosyllabic words spoken by a male speaker. The OLSA has the same matrix-structure as the Hagerman speech test (name-verb-number-adjective-object) and was developed for the German language using a male speaker. Like HINT, GÖSA uses everyday sentences. The sentences have three to seven words and are spoken by a male speaker. In hearing-aid validation, the FMST is to be performed at a fixed SNR of 5 dB with a speech level of 65 dB SPL and a noise level of 60 dB SPL, and results presented in a speech-recognition score ranging from 0 to 100%. The hearing-aid fitting is considered successful when the average measured benefit using two conducted test lists (40 words) is at least 10%-points. OLSA or GÖSA are to be performed at a fixed noise level of 45 dB SPL and an adaptive speech level to measure the SRT. Measurements of unaided and aided speech recognition using OLSA and GÖSA must be conducted in the same spatial loudspeaker configuration. Hearing aids are considered adequate if they provide a benefit of at least 2 dB.

With the Oldenburg Phrases (OLPHRA), Ibelings et al. (2024) developed a novel speech-recognition test based on 4-word phrases with the fixed structure article-adjective-noun-infinitive, e.g., “den grünen Apfel essen” (engl. “eat the green apple”). OLPHRA uses a synthetic female voice, shows a speech rate comparable to the OLSA, consists of frequently used words, and has a phoneme distribution comparable to the average of the German language. In contrast to OLSA, OLPHRA phrases show a semantically predictable context. This is also the case for GÖSA or the HINT. Over 700 phrases and 1000 equivalent test lists (Ibelings et al., 2026) allow for repeated measurements and result in a maximum of one training test list being required. For normal-hearing participants at a fixed noise level of 65 dB SPL, OLPHRA

results on average in a better SRT with -9.1 dB SNR (Ibelings et al., 2024) in comparison to OLSA with -7.1 dB SNR (Wagener et al., 1999) and GÖSA with -6.1 dB SNR (Kollmeier & Wesselkamp, 1997). Overall, in unaided measurements using a female synthetic voice for OLSA and GÖSA, hearing-impaired participants show higher SRTs than normal-hearing participants for the OLPHRA, OLSA, and GÖSA (Ibelings et al., 2026). For hearing-impaired listeners, no significant differences between SRTs measured using OLPHRA and OLSA or between OLPHRA and GÖSA were found (Ibelings et al., 2026). The OLPHRA has not yet been analysed in aided speech-recognition measurements, nor has it been analysed with respect to the evaluation of hearing-aid benefit.

Therefore, the objective of Experiment 1 was to compare OLPHRA to FMST and OLSA with respect to hearing-aid validation. OLPHRA was analysed under the same measurement conditions specified by the hearing-aid guidelines in Germany (G-BA, 2025) for OLSA and GÖSA. The following research questions were addressed in Experiment 1:

- Does OLPHRA show differences of SRTs for unaided or aided measurements in comparison to OLSA?
- Do the measured differences in hearing-aid benefit depend on the speech-recognition test used?

The results from Experiment 1 revealed differences between OLPHRA and OLSA, with the greater hearing-aid benefit measured by OLPHRA. These differences may be due to the different configurations of OLPHRA and OLSA, including the type of speech material, the number of words, the linguistic context, the gender of the speaker, the interfering noise, and the use of a natural or a synthetic voice. To analyse these factors in unaided and aided speech recognition, and therefore the hearing-aid benefit, Experiment 2 was conducted focusing on the speakers' gender, interfering noise, speech synthesis, speech material and presentation level. The respective factors are outlined in the following:

- **Speakers' gender:** For young normal-hearing listeners, better SRTs were observed for female speakers compared to male speakers (Ahrlich, 2013; Bradlow et al., 1996; Hochmuth et al., 2015; Yoho et al., 2019), except for Mönnich et al. (2023) who observed no differences between female and male speaker. For hearing-impaired listeners, Larsby et al. (2015) showed a significant effect of speakers' gender and type of hearing loss (low or high frequency) on speech recognition. In comparison to the male speaker, a female speaker led to poorer SRTs. Furthermore, listeners with high-frequency hearing loss showed a greater difference in SRT for female and male speaker than listeners with low-frequency hearing loss. The effect of the speakers' gender on unaided and the aided speech recognition of hearing-impaired listeners, and therefore hearing-aid benefit, has not yet been considered.
- **Speech synthesis: Text-To-Speech (TTS) systems** enable speech-recognition tests with synthetic voices instead of natural voices (Calandruccio et al., 2025; Ibelings et al., 2022; Nuesse et al., 2019). For normal-hearing listeners, the use of TTS-systems resulted in differences to a natural speaker (Ibelings et al., 2022; Nuesse et al., 2019) that are in range of differences in SRT for different natural speakers (Hochmuth et al., 2015). Ibelings et al. (2026) confirmed the use of TTS systems in unaided speech-recognition measurements with hearing-impaired listeners. The use of TTS systems for hearing-aid performance has not yet been addressed.
- **Speech material:** The structure of OLSA and OLPHRA differs in terms of their word count and the predictability of the sentences or phrases. In this context, Kalikow et al. (1977) demonstrated that speech recognition is affected by the semantic predictability of sentences, with better scores for sentences with high predictability. When comparing median SRTs of the female version of OLSA (Ahrlich, 2013; Nuesse et al., 2019) with OLPHRA (Ibelings et al., 2024), differences in their structure result in practically no relevant differences in SRT for normal-hearing listeners. No effects of the structure of

OLSA and OLPHRA on unaided and aided speech-recognition of hearing-impaired listeners are currently known.

- Interfering noise: For different types of noise masker, Studebaker et al. (1994) demonstrated an effect of the relationship between the noise spectrum and the speech spectrum on speech recognition. For every speech-recognition test, a speech-adjusted noise (SAN) can be generated by superimposing the speech material 30 times to achieve an optimal energetic masking. For different German speech tests, Zinner et al. (2021) demonstrated significant differences in speech recognition using a SAN instead of the standard used interfering noise. In the case of OLSA for normal-hearing listeners, the SAN led to better SRTs in comparison to the standard “olnoise” (Wagener et al., 1999). For hearing-impaired listeners, possible differences in speech recognition depending on the interfering noise (SAN or standard) for OLSA still need to be investigated.
- Presentation level: Adaptive measurements of the SRT can be conducted for different fixed speech or noise levels. Typically, these measurements are conducted at a fixed speech or noise level of 65 dB SPL (e.g., Ibelings et al., 2024; Kollmeier & Wesselkamp, 1997; Nilsson et al., 1994; Wagener et al., 1999). In contrast, the hearing-aid guidelines (G-BA, 2025) in Germany demand a noise level of 45 dB SPL for the measurement of hearing-aid benefit. For normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners, the presentation level of noise has no significant effect on speech recognition when audibility is guaranteed (Wagener & Brand, 2005). However, for hearing-impaired listeners at a low noise level in unaided measurements, an effect of the degree of hearing loss was observed, while in aided measurements the differences in speech recognition were smaller (Hoppe & Hast, 2017; Kollmeier et al., 2011). This resulted in greater hearing-aid benefit for listeners with more profound hearing loss. An effect of the presentation level of the noise on unaided and aided measurements with hearing-impaired listeners, when audibility is not guaranteed, still needs to be investigated.

Overall, the potential influencing factors on speech recognition and therefore hearing-aid benefit raised the following questions:

- Do the
 - gender of the speaker,
 - speech synthesis (natural or synthetic speaker),
 - structure and semantic predictability of the speech material
 - noise type (standard or SAN),
 - and the presentation level of the interfering noise

have an effect on unaided or aided speech recognition and further hearing-aid benefit?

These questions will be addressed here to evaluate the usability of matrix tests (e.g., OLSA) and phrase-based speech-recognition tests having semantic predictability (e.g., OLPHRA) in hearing-aid validation. The focus is on investigating the effect of differences in their configurations on measured hearing-aid benefit.

Experiment 1

Methods

Participants

Twenty-three hearing-impaired participants (10 female, 13 male) took part in speech-recognition measurements. Their age was between 61 and 79 years (median: 75 years) and the pure-tone average thresholds (average of thresholds at 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz, PTA-4) were from 45.6 to 64.4 dB HL (median: 54.7 dB HL). The hearing threshold levels of the participants are shown in the Supplementary Material (Figure S1). All participants were recruited from a database of the Hörzentrum Oldenburg. The compensation was 14 € per hour. The ethics committee (“Kommission für Forschungsfolgenabschätzung und Ethik”) of Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany approved this experiment (Drs. EK/2021/063). Every

participant had German as their first language, at least 3 months hearing-aid experience, and practice in conducting speech-recognition tests like OLSA or FMST.

Equipment

All measurements were carried out in an audiometric booth at Jade University of Applied Sciences in Oldenburg. Pure-tone thresholds were measured with an audiometer (AT700, Auritec, Hamburg, Germany), a soundcard (MAYA22 USB, ESI, Leonberg, Germany), and headphones (HDA 300, Sennheiser, Wedemark, Germany). The speech-recognition measurements were implemented on a laptop in Matlab (Version R2024a, Mathworks, Massachusetts, USA). The sound output was routed via a soundcard (RME Fireface UC, Audio AG, Haimhausen, Germany) to a loudspeaker (type 8030A, Genelec Oy, Isalmi, Finland). The participants were placed at a distance of 1.5 m from the loudspeaker in the frontal direction. For aided speech-recognition measurements, hearing aids Signia Pure C&G 7 IX (WS Audiology, Lyngø, Denmark) with receivers of type M and closed domes were used. Real-ear measurements were carried out using an audiometer Unity 2 (Siemens, Erlangen, Germany) for documenting hearing-aid gains.

Measurement Procedure

At the beginning of the session, general information about the study was provided and consent was obtained. After otoscopy to check for cerumen or abnormalities, the pure-tone thresholds at 0.125, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 6, and 8 kHz were measured. The pure-tone thresholds were used for a first fit of the hearing aids using the fitting formula NAL-NL2. Afterwards, participants were asked whether their perception of loudness with hearing aids was too loud. If the loudness perception was rated as too loud, the broadband gain was reduced by one step in the fitting software, until the participant no longer rated the gain as too loud. This only occurred for one participant, for whom the gain was reduced by two steps. Hearing-aid features were set

to default, whereby wind-noise suppression, frequency compression, and directionality were deactivated.

The speech-recognition measurements were conducted unaided and aided to determine the hearing-aid benefit. To enable a test-retest analysis, two test lists were used for each condition. For speech-recognition measurements with FMST, recordings of Brinkmann (1974) from a Siemens-CD (Erlangen, Germany, article code 7970155 HH 922) were used. Due to lack of test-list equivalence, test lists 1, 3, 5, 8, 11, 12, 15, 17, and 20 were not included (Baljić et al., 2016; DIN 45622-1, 2025; Winkler et al., 2020). The CCITT noise (International Telecommunication Union, 1993), as used in standard practice for FMST measurements in noise, was also used in the current study.

OLSA contains 45 test lists with 20 sentences each. Speech with the original male speaker and noise signal “olnoise” were implemented, as described in Wagener et al. (1999). For the OLPHRA, 1000 test lists are available with 20 phrases per list. As the masker, a SAN, created by 30 times random superimposition of the speech material, was used to maximise energetic masking.

The unaided and aided open-set speech-recognition measurements were conducted with the same signals and sound-pressure levels for each set of speech material. The presentation levels were adapted from the hearing-aid guidelines (G-BA, 2025).

For FMST, a fixed SNR of 5 dB, with a speech level of 65 dB SPL and a noise level of 60 dB SPL was used. However, for the standard recording of the FMST (Brinkmann, 1974) in hearing-aid practice, Winkler & Holube (2016) found a difference in root mean square (RMS) level of 6.5 dB between speech material of FMST and CCITT noise, because the speech material of FMST and CCITT were calibrated to the same peak level, but not the RMS level. Hence, a nominal SNR of 5 dB corresponds to an SNR of -1.5 dB in terms of RMS. OLSA and OLPHRA were calibrated using the corresponding noise signal, so that speech and noise have the same

RMS. Both were conducted at a fixed noise level of 45 dB SPL. The speech level was adapted using the procedure of Brand and Kollmeier (2002). For OLSA, two training test lists were carried out before data collection, and one for OLPHRA. All in all, Experiment 1 consisted of six conditions: unaided and aided measurements of FMST, OLSA, and OLPHRA.

Statistical analysis

For the statistical analysis, Matlab 2024b and SPSS 29 (IBM Corp., Armonk, New York) were used. Speech-recognition results are represented in boxplots, while the horizontal line represents the median, the lower and upper edge of the box the interquartile range and the whiskers minimum and maximum values within 1.5 times the interquartile range. Outliers are indicated with plus symbols. To test data for a normal distribution, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used. The significance level was set to 0.05 for each analysis, and p-values were corrected, if necessary, according to Bonferroni for post-hoc tests.

Due to the different speech-recognition test outcomes (percent correct for FMST and SRTs in dB SNR for OLSA and OLPHRA) a statistical analysis between different speech materials was only performed between OLSA and OLPHRA. The test-retest results were evaluated with the intraclass correlation coefficient and the classification categories of Koo and Li (2016). OLSA and OLPHRA showed good to excellent test-retest reliability (see Supplementary material S2). Therefore, to simplify the evaluation of the results, the mean values from the test and retest of each condition were used for further analysis.

Since no deviations of the speech-recognition data from a normal distribution were detected, the unaided and aided condition of FMST were compared with a paired t-test. To analyse the SRTs between OLSA and OLPHRA, a repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Differences between hearing-aid benefit measured with OLSA and OLPHRA were evaluated with a paired t-test.

Results

Unaided and aided speech-recognition scores of FMST and SRTs of OLSA and OLPHRA are shown in Figure 1. OLPHRA showed higher SRTs in the unaided condition in comparison to OLSA. With aided SRTs being more comparable between OLPHRA and OLSA, a greater hearing-aid benefit resulted for the OLPHRA. The hearing-aid status was significant for the speech-recognition scores of FMST [$t(22) = -6.113, p < 0.001$]. In a comparison of OLSA and OLPHRA, a repeated-measures ANOVA showed a significant effect of the speech test [$F(1,22) = 123.87, p < 0.001$], the hearing-aid status [$F(1,22) = 230.03, p < 0.001$], and the interaction between speech test and hearing-aid status [$F(1,22) = 67.02, p < 0.001$].

Figure 1. Boxplots with medians for unaided and aided speech-recognition outcomes of FMST, OLSA, and OLPHRA, derived from data points determined as the mean of two measured test lists.

Figure 2 shows the hearing-aid benefit, i.e. the difference between aided and unaided measurements for FMST, OLSA, and OLPHRA. For FMST, eight participants were below the threshold for a successful hearing-aid provision according to the hearing-aid guidelines, i.e. 10%-points (G-BA, 2025). For OLSA, there were two participants and for OLPHRA, there were no participant below an improvement of 2 dB in SRT. OLPHRA indicated a significantly

greater hearing-aid benefit in comparison to OLSA [$t(22) = -8.186, p < 0.001$], with a median difference of about 8 dB.

Figure 2. Hearing-aid benefit for FMST, OLSA, and OLPHRA with the indication for a successful hearing aid provision (red line) according to the hearing-aid guidelines (G-BA, 2025) for FMST and OLSA.

Discussion and Conclusion

Experiment 1 was conducted to analyse FMST and OLSA as established speech-recognition tests and the novel speech-recognition test, OLPHRA, for use in hearing-aid validation. The results showed differences in speech recognition, and therefore hearing-aid benefit, depending on the speech material used.

When comparing the hearing-aid benefit of FMST and OLSA in relation to the respective threshold for a successful hearing-aid provision according to the hearing-aid guidelines (G-BA, 2025), FMST did not indicate success regarding the speech-recognition benefit with hearing aids in some cases, whereas the OLSA did. This raises the question of the extent to which the FMST can reflect the benefit in speech recognition in noise for the group of participants examined. To make a more detailed statement about the use of FMST in hearing-aid validation, it would be necessary to examine further types of hearing loss and other age groups.

Nevertheless, the present results indicate that OLSA is more sensitive than FMST in detecting a hearing-aid benefit.

OLPHRA indicated a significantly greater hearing-aid benefit than OLSA. This resulted from the much higher SRTs in the unaided condition of OLPHRA, and comparable SRTs in the aided condition (see Figure 1). Contrarily, Ibelings et al. (2026) showed no significant differences between OLSA and OLPHRA in unaided measurements at a noise level of 65 dB SPL with hearing-impaired participants, whereby they used the OLSA with a synthetic female voice. At this point, no clear reason for the differences between OLPHRA and OLSA in the results obtained at a fixed noise level of 45 dB SPL could be identified. The following factors could have influenced speech recognition, and therefore hearing-aid benefit, and may explain the difference between OLPHRA and OLSA:

- Comparison of a male natural speaker in OLSA and a female synthetic speaker in OLPHRA in participants exhibiting high-frequency hearing loss
- Effects of audibility due to the noise level of 45 dB SPL
- OLPHRA uses a SAN for maximised energetic masking, while the original OLSA shows differences in speech and noise spectrum of about 3 dB from 500 Hz upwards (Zinner et al., 2021).
- OLPHRA contains significantly more words in the available corpus than OLSA (Ibelings et al., 2024). In addition, participants were familiar with the conduction of tests using, and the limited vocabulary of, the OLSA.

To analyse these possible factors influencing the hearing-aid validation, further measurements at noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL were conducted in a subsequent Experiment 2, with participants having a similar hearing loss as in Experiment 1 and using different versions of the OLSA and the OLPHRA.

Experiment 2

Methods

In many respects, the methods correspond to those used in Experiment 1. Therefore, only deviations are described in the following.

Participants

For Experiment 2, 15 participants of Experiment 1 were re-recruited. Additionally, eight further hearing-impaired participants were recruited, resulting in a total number of 23 participants in Experiment 2. These participants were aged between 60 and 78 years (median: 75 years) and had a PTA-4 ranging from 44.4 to 67.5 dB HL (median: 56.3 dB HL). Supplementary Figure S3 displays the hearing-threshold levels of these participants. This experiment was also approved by the ethics committee (Kommission für Forschungsfolgenabschätzung und Ethik) at Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, Germany (Drs EK/2025/026).

Measurement Procedure

The noise reduction of the hearing aids was deactivated in Experiment 2. Broadband gain was reduced by one step in the fitting software for three participants. Unlike Experiment 1, the speech-recognition measurement only included one test list for each measurement condition.

In order to analyse the effect of the speakers' gender, the noise signal used, and speech synthesis, the OLSA was implemented in four different versions:

- Male speaker, original noise “olnoise” (OLSA_m_orig): OLSA_m_orig was implemented in the same way as in Experiment 1. Due to the original generation of the noise signal before the optimisation of the speech material, the spectra of speech and noise differed up to about 3 dB (Zinner et al., 2021).

- Male speaker, SAN (OLSA_m_SAN): OLSA_m_SAN had the same speaker as OLSA_m_orig, but the SAN was created by randomly superimposing the speech material 30 times to maximize energetic masking.
- Female speaker (Ahrlich, 2013), SAN (OLSA_f_SAN): Using the implementation employed by Nuesse et al. (2019), with the additional generation of a SAN.
- Synthetic female speaker (Nuesse et al., 2019), SAN (OLSA_synth_f_SAN): Implemented in a manner consistent with the approach employed by Nuesse et al. (2019).

All OLSA versions contained 45 test lists with 20 sentences each. All measurements of OLPHRA and OLSA were conducted for two fixed noise levels, at 45 dB SPL and at 65 dB SPL. With unaided and aided measurements, this led to overall 20 measurement conditions in Experiment 2.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis was divided into four parts, depending on the research question. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test did not reveal any significant deviation from a normal distribution, except for the unaided condition of OLSA_m_orig with a noise level of 65 dB SPL. To investigate the effect of the speaker's gender, a comparison was made between the versions *OLSA_m_SAN* and *OLSA_f_SAN*. Possible differences between natural and synthetic speech synthesis were examined by evaluating the versions *OLSA_f_SAN* and *OLSA_synth_f_SAN*. *OLPHRA* and *OLSA_synth_f_SAN* were compared, to analyse the effects of the speech material on speech recognition. The effect of the noise signal used was analysed comparing *OLSA_m_orig* and *OLSA_m_SAN*. In all cases, a repeated-measures ANOVA with the factors level, hearing-aid status, and a specific factor depending on the research question, was performed. Subsequently, differences in speech recognition were further analysed using post-

hoc t-tests. The significance level was set to 0.05 and corrected according to Bonferroni for post-hoc tests.

Results

The SRTs for the unaided and aided measurements at the two fixed noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL for the OLPHRA and all versions of the OLSA are shown in Figure 3. The statistical analysis with repeated-measures ANOVA for the four comparisons to answer the research questions is shown in Table 1.

The comparison of *OLSA_m_SAN* and *OLSA_f_SAN* for speakers' gender was significant for all factors and interactions of factors. Post-hoc tests showed no significant differences in SRT in the aided measurement with a fixed noise level of 45 dB SPL, nor in the unaided and aided with a fixed noise level of 65 dB SPL, but differences in the unaided 45 dB SPL condition (see Supplementary Table S4.1).

Comparing *OLSA_f_SAN* and *OLSA_synth_f_SAN*, level, hearing-aid status, and the interaction of both factors were significant. Also, the factor synthesis alone showed a significant effect, whereby all interactions with synthesis resulted in non-significant results. The post-hoc tests (see Supplementary Table S4.3) displayed no significant differences between *OLSA_f_SAN* and *OLSA_synth_f_SAN* with the same level and hearing-aid status.

In the case of *OLPHRA* and *OLSA_synth_f_SAN*, the results showed significant differences for all factors and interactions, with the exception of the interaction of all three factors. Post-hoc tests revealed significant differences between the unaided and aided measurements at a noise level of 45 dB SPL and the unaided measurement at a noise level of 65 dB SPL. The difference between the aided measurements with a noise level of 65 dB SPL was non-significant.

For *OLSA_m_orig* and *OLSA_m_SAN*, the factor noise, the interaction of noise and hearing-aid status, and the interaction of all factors noise, hearing-aid status, and noise used showed no

significant results. In contrast, the interaction of noise and level was significant. Pairwise comparisons of the measurement conditions revealed no significant differences in SRT for the unaided and aided 45 dB SPL noise conditions and the unaided 65 dB SPL condition. The aided measurements at a noise level of 65 dB SPL showed significant differences (see Supplementary Table S4.2), with a median difference of 0.7 dB.

In summary, the four previous repeated-measures ANOVA consistently showed a significant effect of the noise level when the unaided and the aided conditions were separately compared.

Figure 3. Unaided and aided SRTs at noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL for OLPHRA and four versions of OLSA: OLSA_m_orig, OLSA_m_SAN, OLSA_f_SAN, and OLSA_synth_f_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic).

Table 1. Results of repeated-measures ANOVA for the four comparisons of OLSA_m_SAN and OLSA_f_SAN to analyse the effect of speakers' gender, OLSA_f_SAN and OLSA_synth_f_SAN to analyse the effect of the speech synthesis, OLPHRA and OLSA_synth_f_SAN to analyse the effect of the speech material on speech-recognition, and OLSA_m_orig and OLSA_m_SAN to analyse the effect of the noise signal used (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic).

Comparison	Factor	df	F-value	p-value
OLSA_m_SAN vs. OLSA_f_SAN	Level	1,22	382.932	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		130.158	< 0.001*
	Gender		28.286	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status		55.957	< 0.001*
	Level*Gender		18.567	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status*Gender		27.029	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Gender		15.173	< 0.001*
OLSA_f_SAN vs. OLSA_synth_f_SAN	Level	1,22	447.622	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		197.890	< 0.001*
	Synthesis		8.309	0.009*
	Level*Hearing-aid status		82.157	< 0.001*
	Level*Synthesis		0.013	0.910
	Hearing aid status*Synthesis		0.348	0.561
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Synthesis		0.001	0.980
OLPHRA vs. OLSA_synth_f_SAN	Level	1,22	611.079	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		255.859	< 0.001*
	Speech material		36.894	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status		62.438	< 0.001*
	Level*Speech material		15.249	< 0.001*
	Hearing aid status*Speech material		22.324	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Speech material		0.013	0.911
OLSA_m_orig vs. OLSA_m_SAN	Level	1,22	205.105	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		85.669	< 0.001*
	Noise		3.508	0.074
	Level*Hearing-aid status		30.883	< 0.001*
	Level*Noise		5.750	0.025*
	Hearing aid status*Noise		3.412	0.078
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Noise		1.994	0.172

Figure 4 displays the hearing-aid benefit of the OLPHRA and all four versions of the OLSA resulting from unaided and aided measurements from Figure 3. An overview of the results of the repeated-measures ANOVAs is given in Supplementary Table S5.1.

When comparing *OLSA_m_SAN* and *OLSA_f_SAN*, repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a significant effect on hearing-aid benefit of level, speakers' gender, and the interaction of level and speakers' gender. Post-hoc tests indicated significant differences between all conditions, but not between the hearing-aid benefit at a noise level of 65 dB SPL (see Supplementary Table S5.2).

In the analysis of *OLSA_f_SAN* and *OLSA_synth_f_SAN*, the level was the only significant factor. Speech synthesis and the interaction of level and speech synthesis showed no significant effect on hearing-aid benefit. Also, the post-hoc tests resulted in no significant differences between the hearing-aid benefit for a noise level of 45 and 65 dB SPL (see Supplementary Table S5.4).

To consider the influence of the speech material with *OLPHRA* and *OLSA_synth_f_SAN*, the level and the speech material revealed a significant effect. The interaction of the two factors was not significant. The post-hoc tests showed significant differences between all conditions (see Supplementary Table S5.5).

In the comparison of *OLSA_m_orig* and *OLSA_m_SAN*, only the level showed a significant effect, but not the noise or the interaction of both factors. Pairwise comparisons showed significant differences for all conditions, except for the hearing-aid benefit for a noise level of 45 dB SPL (see Supplementary Table S5.3).

Figure 3. Hearing-aid benefit at noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL for OLPHRA and four versions of OLSA: OLSA_m_orig, OLSA_m_SAN, OLSA_f_SAN, and OLSA_synth_f_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic).. The red line indicates a successful hearing-aid provision according to the hearing aid guidelines when using the OLSA for hearing-aid validation (G-BA, 2025).

Discussion

In Experiment 2, the unaided and aided speech recognition was measured for hearing-impaired participants with differences in the speech-recognition tests with respect to the speakers' gender, the speech synthesis, the speech material, the interfering noise, and the noise level. The following sections discuss these individual effects on speech recognition in noise and therefore the hearing-aid benefit with regard to the hearing-aid validation. Finally, in a general discussion, the influence of the speech-recognition test configurations is summarised, and the usability of matrix tests and phrase-based speech-recognition tests with semantic predictability for hearing-aid validation evaluated.

Speakers' gender

When comparing the unaided and aided measurements at noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL of the OLSA with a male and a female speaker separately, only a significant difference for the unaided condition at 45 dB SPL noise level was found. In this condition, the female speaker led

to poorer SRTs than the male speaker. This finding is consistent with the results of Larsby et al. (2015), where the female voice also resulted in poorer unaided speech recognition in noise in comparison to the male voice for hearing-impaired listeners with a high-frequency hearing loss. The large inter-individual SRT differences in the unaided 45 dB SPL condition indicate problems with audibility (Wagener & Brand, 2005), which may have a greater impact for the female than for the male speaker, because of the interaction between the high-frequency hearing loss and the greater energy of higher-frequency components in the female voice.

Under conditions where audibility presumably is given, (aided 45 dB SPL, unaided and aided, 65 dB SPL) no differences between the female and male speaker were found. Mönnich et al. (2023) also found no differences in speech recognition for normal-hearing listeners when audibility was assumed for both female and male speakers. In other studies, the speech recognition in quiet (Bradlow et al., 1996) and in noise (Wagener et al, 1999; Ahrlich et al., 2013; Yoho et al., 2019) for normal-hearing listeners was better for the female speaker than for the male. This may not have been detectable in this study due to uncompensated deficits in speech recognition with hearing aids.

In comparison to the male speaker, hearing-aid benefit was only significantly greater for the female speaker at a noise level of 45 dB SPL, which was due to the higher SRTs in the unaided condition at a noise level of 45 dB SPL. Also, a greater inter-individual difference in SRT was found for the female speaker at a noise level of 45 dB SPL. All in all, the results indicate the benefits of using a female voice for hearing-aid validation to measure a greater hearing-aid benefit, investigate problems in audibility, and achieve a better differentiation in hearing-aid benefit between participants.

Speech synthesis

A comparison of the female OLSA with a natural and synthetic voice resulted in no significant differences in speech recognition and hearing-aid benefit. These results are in agreement with

both findings of Nuesse et al. (2019) for the female OLSA and of Ibelings et al. (2022) for the GÖSA for normal-hearing listeners. The results in this study confirm the usage of TTS systems in speech-recognition tests, also for unaided and aided measurements with hearing-impaired listeners, and therefore in practice for hearing-aid validation measurements.

Speech material

The SRTs for the OLPHRA and OLSA_synth_f_SAN showed significant differences for all conditions, except the aided condition with a noise level of 65 dB SPL. Under conditions with significant differences, the OLPHRA resulted in poorer SRTs than the OLSA. In unaided measurements at a fixed noise level of 65 dB SPL for hearing-impaired listeners with slightly better hearing than in the current study, Ibelings et al. (2026) found no differences between OLPHRA and female synthetic OLSA. The significant differences at a noise level of 65 dB SPL in the present unaided measurements may be due to the greater hearing loss of the participants. In combination with the aspect of the hearing loss, it can be assumed that the extensive experience of the participants with the OLSA and the training effect, resulting from the limited speech material, led to better SRTs for the OLSA in comparison to the unknown OLPHRA with a greater corpus and many test lists. Possible effects of problems with audibility could also be a further reason for the differences between OLPHRA and OLSA_synth_f_SAN. This may be indicated by no significant differences in speech recognition in the aided measurement at a noise level of 65 dB SPL.

The hearing-aid benefit was significantly greater in both conditions at noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL for the OLPHRA, which results from the significantly poorer SRTs in the unaided conditions in comparison to the OLSA_synth_f_SAN. To obtain a greater hearing-aid benefit in practice, the speech-recognition test with semantically predictable phrases (OLPHRA) should be preferred over the matrix test (OLSA).

Noise

For the standard noise and the SAN, no significant differences in speech recognition were found in post-hoc tests, except for the aided condition with a noise level of 65 dB SPL resulting in a difference of 0.7 dB, which is in range of the uncertainty of the OLSA. For normal-hearing participants, Zinner et al. (2021) showed a 2.2 dB better speech-recognition for the OLSA when using the SAN in comparison to the standard noise. In the current study, for hearing-impaired participants with high-frequency hearing loss, no practically relevant differences between the standard noise and SAN were observed. This may be because of a not fully compensated hearing loss above 500 Hz, where differences between the standard noise and the SAN are present, and the hearing loss of the participants is most prominent. The noise type also showed no significant effect on hearing-aid benefit.

Noise level

The presentation level of the noise significantly influenced the speech recognition and hearing-aid benefit under all considerations. A low noise level of 45 dB SPL led to significantly poorer speech recognition for all speech materials, resulting in a greater hearing-aid benefit in comparison to a noise level of 65 dB SPL. Wagener & Brand (2005) could not detect differences in speech recognition for different presentation levels, whereby the audibility for hearing-impaired listeners was ensured by using presentation levels that were perceived at least as 'soft' on a loudness scale. The present study did not ensure audibility, as can be seen from the greater spread of SRTs in the results of the measurements conducted at a noise level of 45 dB SPL. The effect of the lack of audibility confirms the results of Kollmeier et al. (2011) and Hoppe and Hast (2017), where a greater hearing loss led to poorer speech recognition for the OLSA/GÖSA at a noise level of 45 dB SPL. A greater hearing loss also resulted in greater hearing-aid benefit. Kollmeier et al. (2011) also found that the greatest benefit from hearing aids was achieved at the lowest noise level considered (45, 50, or 55 dB SPL). These findings are consistent with the

results of the present study. In summary, to obtain a greater hearing-aid benefit in hearing-aid validation, the use of a low noise level (e.g., 45 dB SPL) should be considered.

General discussion

The current work illustrates that hearing-aid validation can lead to different outcomes, depending on the configurations of the speech-recognition tests used. This shows the relevance of standardised procedures in speech-recognition measurements in hearing-aid practice. Therefore, it is recommended that the speech test used and its configuration be documented. This would enable an improved evaluation of hearing-aid benefit and comparability of outcomes. All in all, both the phrase-based speech-recognition test with semantic predictability (OLPHRA) and the matrix test (OLSA) showed no deficits in indicating a benefit in speech recognition with hearing aids. With a smaller training effect, semantically predictable phrases, and greater hearing-aid benefit, OLPHRA shows advantages over OLSA for hearing-aid validation.

Conclusion

Speech-recognition measurements in the context of hearing-aid validation show significant differences when varying the speech material, the gender of the speaker, and the presentation level. These configurations also had an impact on the measured hearing-aid benefit. The type of noise (standard or SAN) and speech synthesis (natural or synthetic voice) had no effect on speech recognition and hearing-aid benefit for hearing-impaired participants having a high-frequency hearing loss. Overall, a female speaker at a low noise level of 45 dB SPL led to greater hearing-aid benefit and a better differentiation between participants than a male speaker and a noise level of 65 dB SPL. Furthermore, the speech material with fixed structure and semantically predictable phrases (OLPHRA) appeared to be more sensitive in detecting a hearing-aid benefit.

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Disclosure statement

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Data availability statement

Data are available on reasonable request from the authors.

Authors' Note

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Comparison	Factor	df	F-value	p-value
OLSA_m_SAN vs. OLSA_f_SAN	Level	1,22	382.932	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		130.158	< 0.001*
	Gender		28.286	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status		55.957	< 0.001*
	Level*Gender		18.567	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status*Gender		27.029	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Gender		15.173	< 0.001*
OLSA_f_SAN vs. OLSA_synth_f_SAN	Level	1,22	447.622	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		197.890	< 0.001*
	Synthesis		8.309	0.009*
	Level*Hearing-aid status		82.157	< 0.001*
	Level*Synthesis		0.013	0.910
	Hearing aid status*Synthesis		0.348	0.561
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Synthesis		0.001	0.980
OLPHRA vs. OLSA_synth_f_SAN	Level	1,22	611.079	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		255.859	< 0.001*
	Speech material		36.894	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status		62.438	< 0.001*
	Level*Speech material		15.249	< 0.001*
	Hearing aid status*Speech material		22.324	< 0.001*
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Speech material		0.013	0.911
OLSA_m_orig vs. OLSA_m_SAN	Level	1,22	205.105	< 0.001*
	Hearing-aid status		85.669	< 0.001*
	Noise		3.508	0.074
	Level*Hearing-aid status		30.883	< 0.001*
	Level*Noise		5.750	0.025*
	Hearing aid status*Noise		3.412	0.078
	Level*Hearing-aid status*Noise		1.994	0.172

Table Captions

Table 1. Results of repeated-measures ANOVA for the four comparisons of OLSA_m_SAN and OLSA_f_SAN to analyse the effect of speakers' gender, OLSA_m_orig and OLSA_m_SAN to analyse the effect of the used noise signal, OLSA_f_SAN and OLSA_synth_f_SAN to analyse the effect of the speech synthesis and OLPHRA and OLSA_synth_f_SAN to analyse the effect of the speech material on speech-recognition (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic)

Figure Captions

Figure 4. Boxplots with medians for unaided and aided speech-recognition outcomes of FMST, OLSA, and OLPHRA, derived from data points determined as the mean of two measured test lists.

Figure 5. Hearing-aid benefit for FMST, OLSA, and OLPHRA with the indication for a successful hearing aid provision (red line) according to the hearing-aid guidelines (G-BA, 2025) for FMST and OLSA.

Figure 3. Unaided and aided SRTs at noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL for OLPHRA and four versions of OLSA: OLSA_m_orig, OLSA_m_SAN, OLSA_f_SAN, and OLSA_synth_f_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic).

Figure 6. Hearing-aid benefit at noise levels of 45 and 65 dB SPL for OLPHRA and four versions of OLSA: OLSA_m_orig, OLSA_m_SAN, OLSA_f_SAN, and OLSA_synth_f_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic). The red line indicates a successful hearing-aid provision according to the hearing aid guidelines when using the OLSA for hearing-aid validation (G-BA, 2025).

S1: Pure-tone thresholds of participants in Experiment 1

Figure S1.1. Pure-tone thresholds of the 23 participants of the right (red) and left (blue) ear.

S2: Test-retest Reliability

Figure S2.1. Comparison of the first measurement (M1) and the second measurement (M2) for all unaided (left) and aided (right) conditions. The horizontal line represents perfect alignment of the measurements. Specification of the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) with respective significance (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

With the criteria of Koo & Li (2016) the reliability of the unaided and aided conditions are depicted in Table S2.1.

Table S2.1. Test-retest reliability according to the criteria of Koo & Li (2016) for unaided and aided conditions of FBE, OLSA and OLPHRA

	FBE	OLSA	OLPHRA
Unaided	poor	excellent	good
Aided	moderate	excellent	excellent

S3: Pure-tone thresholds of participants in Experiment 2

Figure S3.1. Pure-tone thresholds of the 23 participants of the right (red) and left (blue) ear.

S5: Statistical analysis of hearing aid benefit in Experiment 2

Table S5.1. Results of repeated-measures ANOVA for the four comparisons of OLSA_m_SAN and OLSA_f_SAN to analyse the effect of speakers' gender, OLSA_m_orig and OLSA_m_SAN to analyse the effect of the used noise signal, OLSA_f_SAN and OLSA_synth_f_SAN to analyse the effect of the speech synthesis and OLPHRA and OLSA_synth_f_SAN to analyse the effect of the speech material hearing aid benefit (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic).

Comparison	Factor	df	F-value	p-value
OLSA_m_SAN vs. OLSA_f_SAN	Level	1,22	55.957	< 0.001*
	Gender		27.029	< 0.001*
	Level*Gender		15.173	< 0.001*
OLSA_m_orig vs. OLSA_m_SAN	Level	1,22	30.883	< 0.001*
	Noise		3.412	0.078
	Level*Noise		1.994	0.172
OLSA_f_SAN vs. OLSA_synth_f_SAN	Level	1,22	82.157	< 0.001*
	Synthesis		0.348	0.561
	Level*Synthesis		0.001	0.980
OLPHRA vs. OLSA_synth_f_SAN	Level	1,22	62.438	< 0.001*
	Speech material		22.324	< 0.001*
	Level*Speech material		0.013	0.911

Table S5.2. Results of pairwise t-tests of hearing aid benefit in all conditions of OLSA_m_SAN and OLSA_f_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic). Significant results are indicated with an asterisk.

	Olsa_m_SAN_45	Olsa_m_SAN_65	Olsa_f_SAN_45	Olsa_f_SAN_65
Olsa_m_SAN_45		t(22) = 5.009 p < 0.001*	t(22) = -5.123 p < 0.001*	t(22) = 3.415 p = 0.015*
Olsa_m_SAN_65			t(22) = -9.444 p < 0.001*	t(22) = -2.838 p = 0.057
Olsa_f_SAN_45				t(22) = 8.489 p < 0.001*
Olsa_f_SAN_65				

Table S5.3. Results of pairwise t-tests of hearing aid benefit in all conditions of OLSA_m_orig and OLSA_m_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic). Significant results are indicated with an asterisk.

	Olsa_m_orig_45	Olsa_m_orig_65	Olsa_m_SAN_45	Olsa_m_SAN_65
Olsa_m_orig_45		t(22) = 5.660 p < 0.001*	t(22) = -0.418 p = 1.000	t(22) = 4.475 p = 0.001*
Olsa_m_orig_65			t(22) = -6.050 p < 0.001*	t(22) = -4.201 p = 0.002*
Olsa_m_SAN_45				t(22) = 5.009 p < 0.001*
Olsa_m_SAN_65				

Table S5.4. Results of pairwise t-tests of hearing aid benefit in all conditions of OLSA_f_SAN and OLSA_synth_f_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic). Significant results are indicated with an asterisk.

	Olsa_f_SAN_45	Olsa_f_SAN_65	Olsa_synth_f_45	Olsa_synth_f_65
Olsa_f_SAN_45		t(22) = 8,489 p < 0,001*	t(22) = 0,347 p = 1,000	t(22) = 7,150 p < 0,001*
Olsa_f_SAN_65			t(22) = -9,187 p < 0,001*	t(22) = 0,583 p = 1,000
Olsa_synth_f_45				t(22) = 7,615 p < 0,001*
Olsa_synth_f_65				

Table S5.5. Results of pairwise t-tests of hearing aid benefit in all conditions of OLPHRA and OLSA_synth_f_SAN (m = male, f = female, SAN = Speech Adjusted Noise, orig = original noise, synth = synthetic). Significant results are indicated with an asterisk.

	Olphra_45	Olphra_65	Olsa_w_TTS_45	Olsa_w_TTS_65
Olphra_45		t(22) = 6.858 p < 0.001*	t(22) = 2.964 p = 0.043*	t(22) = 10.293 p < 0.001*
Olphra_65			t(22) = -4.214 p = 0.002*	t(22) = 5.196 p < 0.001*
Olsa_w_TTS_45				t(22) = 7.615 p < 0.001*
Olsa_w_TTS_65				

References

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